

**STRATEGIES EMPLOYED BY THE SELECTED
INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS TO
ADDRESS THE EMERGING CASES OF EARLY
TEENAGE PREGNANCIES IN THE ALABAT ISLAND
DIVISION OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR LOCALIZED
GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

2023

Volume: 10

Pages: 168-187

Document ID: 2023PEMJ843

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8093804

Manuscript Accepted: 2023-28-6

Strategies Employed by the Selected Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Emerging Cases of Early Teenage Pregnancies in the Alabat Island Division of Quezon: Basis for Localized Gender and Development Program

Jhohnniel P. Celeste*, Randy T. Nobleza

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study has made to gather data regarding on the strategies employed by the selected internal and external stakeholders to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancy in the Alabat Island Division of Quezon. Thus; the study sought to answer the following, what strategies are being employed by the internal and external stakeholders and what are the results of their strategies. The strategic solution for untimely pregnancy of teenagers was the spotlight of the study where these teenagers are secondary students. The internal stakeholders were composed of District GAD coordinators, District Nurses, School GAD coordinators, Secondary Teachers, Health coordinators, ARH coordinators and guidance counselors. In contrast, external stakeholders were the DSWD Pantawid head, MSWDO head, Health Officer, and SK Federation President, WCPD officer, and Secondary parents, who took significant part in the study. With the data gathered, researcher; has come up to a recommendation of programs for the Alabat Island Division of Quezon. The study utilized qualitative methods to come up with better outcomes, which has been done through group interviews. Hence, the sampling design was purposeful sampling to get the most appropriate participants of the study. The study has been conducted in the whole island; that, composed of three municipalities, Perez, Alabat, and Quezon. With the help of thematic analysis of the data, the study has been more organized and meaningful. The results of the strategies employed by the internal and external stakeholders in Alabat island appeared as the comprehensive sex education, abstinence strategy, counseling, youth social development, contraceptive counseling, awareness on rights and protection of the youth, no cellphone policy inside the classroom, parenthood development program and case management. As conclusion, the internal and external stakeholders focus on spreading awareness about topics relating to sex education, such as understanding changes that happened in puberty, proper use of contraceptives, and giving knowledge about HIV and STDs. However, despite the continuous implementation of these strategies, it appears that the emerging cases of teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island continue to increase. As recommendation, since the teenage pregnancy increase in general, the Internal and external stakeholders may continue to initiate multifaceted long-term programs educating the local public on the severe social and public health consequences of unwanted pregnancy. In addition, since the most encountered problems of the stakeholders were the parents' participation, beliefs and guidance, stakeholders may also consider further programs focusing on proper parenthood and family support to help parents or guardians establish a positive relationship with their children.

Keywords: *gender and development, internal and external stakeholders, teenage pregnancy, and strategies*

Introduction

UNESCO identified sustainable development goals in 2015, and five of these are (1) For families to able to provide foods on their table regularly, (2) To have no gnawing of the stomach, (3) To have physical wellness and good welfare, (4) To attain equal opportunity and continuing education for all and (5) To achieve equality among all genders and for empowered women by 2030, United Nations (2015). Teenage pregnancy is one of the most pressing matters confronting today's Filipino youth. World Health Organization (2018) claimed that, pregnancy among teenagers is a global youth development issue and early pregnancy and the

implications of delivering a child to young girls are major factors in death. They are usually experiencing violence which eventually leads to dropping out of school.

According to a 2016 UNFPA-commissioned study, adolescents in the Philippines who started childbirth before 18 are much less likely to graduate from secondary school than adolescents who did not start childbearing. Adolescent pregnancy is a significant issue in many of our communities. Numerous adolescents choose to engage in sexual activity before they are capable of committing to loving relationships (UNFPA, 2016). Briones (2019) claimed that one of the root causes of the high dropout rate of girls is

marriage and family matters, which also can be treated as teenage pregnancy. In relation, Duterte (2021) has inscribed that teenage pregnancy is a national priority as stated to in presidential order number 141 (E. O. 141). Hence, all government agencies and instrumentalities shall identify and implement as far as practicable interventions related to the prevention of Adolescent pregnancies. For the year 2020, POPCOM and DepEd, together with Adolescent Pregnancy Technical Working Group (APTWG) make a rigorous effort to reach more adolescents by providing age-appropriate information and services and eventually decline the incidence of teenage pregnancy in the region (Obcena, 2020).

In addition, as mandated by the 2021 General Appropriations Act, the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) and the Commission on Population and Development (POPCOM) implemented the Social Protection Program for Teenage Mothers and their Children (SPPTMC). This collaboration has strengthened by a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) which aiming to establish a social safety net program specifically for minor teenage mothers and their children. As initially intended in the Philippine Development Plan and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, SPPTMC seeks to prevent teenage pregnancies and to establish adequate and available measures to protect the well-being of teenage mothers and their children. The DSWD and POPCOM both recognize the importance of preventing teen pregnancy because of the long-term consequences on the health of young people in a population group that is critical to national development (Fawcett et al. 2017). Furthermore, several DepEd Memorandum Orders have also provided programs and guidelines as a way in battling the same issue. The D. M. No. 101, s. 2019 entitled “KAPIT-KAMAY: EMPOWERING THE YOUTH TO MAKE INFORMED CHOICES,” aims to convene a summit to discuss the educational, health, and developmental dimensions of early pregnancy issues. The Division Memorandum No. 196, s. 2021 of Region IV-A Schools Division of Quezon Province entitled “ONLINE ADOLESCENT HEALTH AND DEVELOPMENT (AHD) PROGRAM IN DEPED-QUEZON (PILOT ACTIVITY)” aims to raise awareness among adolescent learners about appropriate information about adolescent sexuality and other reproductive health concerns and issues through the Teenage Pregnancy Symposium as well as the AHD Film Distribution.

Moreover, the DO No. 031, s. 2018 entitled “POLICY GUIDELINES ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COMPREHENSIVE SEXUALITY

EDUCATION,” aims to achieve a common understanding of the CSE's key concepts and messages, as well as to ensure precise protocol implementation in the CSE. In connection, Memorandum No. 150, s. 2020 Division of Quezon, titled Division Policy Guidelines on the implementing of Gender and Development (GAD) programs, projects and activities, as compliance to Republic Act 9710 or Magna Carta for Women (MCW) and DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2017 or Gender-Responsive Basic Education Policy, stated that the division of Quezon is dedicated to ensuring that all gender issues are adequately addressed where no employee and learners are left behind in the organization. Ensuring capacity for advancement and procedure that are collaborative, developmental, provides equality, strategic, no violence, exercise human rights, asserting confidence, and develop the wholistic individual. Division of Quezon also committed that learning resource GAD focal persons are well-trained on gender responsiveness, sexuality, reproductive health education, human rights, and peace education. (Mohr, 2019) Study titled, The Influence of Educational Attainment on Teenage Pregnancy in Low-Income Countries: A Systematic Literature Review, claimed that, teenagers who have higher education or remained in school longer generally delayed being pregnant at an early age than other females who had little or no education at all. Hence, the study recommended that a well-established country should come to an understanding what factors affect teenagers' becoming dropouts, which could be a reasonable basis for the interventions in combating the issue. Therefore, the stakeholders must unflinchingly and untiringly instill the moral values. The classroom may be the best place to discuss the negative impact of early pregnancy but it can also be taught via online platforms and to the community. The educators and school collaborators must reiterate to students about the significance of finishing their studies. (Manila Times 2020) stated that, if there are programs tackling about the teenage pregnancy in a more responsible way, this would be the basic step to reduce ballooning cases of the unintended pregnancy of teenagers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to seek the Strategies Employed by the Selected Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Emerging Cases of Teenage Pregnancies in the Alabat Island Division of Quezon as a basis for the Localized Gender and Development Program. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the strategies employed by the internal and external stakeholders to address the emerging cases of

teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island, Division of Quezon in terms of:

- 1.1 types of strategies;
 - 1.2 means or ways of implementation;
 - 1.3 frequency of implementation; and
 - 1.4 other action taken?
2. What are the results of the strategies employed by the internal and external stakeholders in addressing teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island, Division of Quezon in terms of:
- 2.1 number of teenage pregnancy cases in the years 2021 and 2022;
 - 2.2 problems encountered in the implementation;
 - 2.3 coping mechanism to address factors affecting implementation; and
 - 2.4 effects of the teenage pregnancy program?
3. What localized GAD intervention program could be proposed by the researcher in addressing emerging cases of teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island, Division of Quezon?

Methodology

This section covers information about how the researcher carried out the study. It involved the design, techniques, and strategies utilized in the study. It also included the sample population and the research tool and provided information on the data analysis. This chapter gave an in-depth explanation of the various processes conducted to achieve the aims of the study.

Research Design

A qualitative and quantitative study were employed in this research. The qualitative was done through phenomenological research design to gather universal essence of phenomenon from focus group discussion, while quantitative study was done through getting the frequency of the responses and come up with the interpretation and thematic analysis. It is worth to elaborate the phenomenological approach of the study as it had a great effect on the research's data gathering. Phenomenological approach ought to provide detailed information on the experiences of a population about a certain question. In other words, phenomenological research studies lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how people understand those experiences (Delve, 2020). The design ought to gather information through the interview, which paved the way for the researcher to obtain participants' experiences and challenges on the studied matter. This method design was appropriate to this specific study as it allowed the researcher to gather and discuss the experiences of the participants and obtain the needed information.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Alabat Island, Quezon province, in the eastern portion of Quezon. It has three municipalities, Perez, Alabat, and Quezon, with an estimated population of 47,000 (PhilAtlas, 2020). Likewise, Quezon is ranked four among the most populated provinces in Region IV-A CALABARZON and third with the most cases of teenage pregnancy in the region (PSA, 2020). Alabat Island, as part of Quezon, also had alarming cases of teenage pregnancies. According to the data given by the rural health workers of the three municipalities, in 2020, the whole island recorded 111 cases, while in 2021, it recorded 83 cases. In 2022 as of the second quarter, the island recorded 73 cases. The case number goes up and down and is still obviously increasing. With this, the data only show that the Island is significantly contributing to the emerging cases of teenage pregnancies in the whole province of Quezon. This is one of the main significant matters why the Island as part of Quezon has to be studied, to know how the internal and external stakeholders of the teenagers in the secondary level school are taking action with this concern. Nonetheless, the people of the island are welcoming and happy. The island also has developing towns but also reflects poverty. According to GovPh (2021), the three municipalities belong to fifth-class municipalities. However, the towns have stunning sceneries and different cultures, beliefs, functions, livelihoods, and traditions, caused mainly by geographical location provided with mountain ranges and several natural landscapes.

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study were only the selected internal and external stakeholders. In Quezon, there were six (6) internal and five (5) external participants with a total of 11 individuals, while in Alabat, there were six (6) external and six (6) internal participants with a total of 12 individuals, and in Perez, there were six (6) internal and six (6) external participants with the total of 12 individuals, in summation there were 35 stakeholders as participants. The researcher used the purposive sampling technique to select the participants according to their roles in their groups. This sampling technique has been suitable for the study to evaluate data from the group representative. It also allowed the study to quickly obtain a sample population that best represents the entire population being studied.

Research Instruments

This study used a guide-question instrument for the qualitative method. The researcher, for the qualitative, formulated couple of guide questions to gather the

strategies that the internal and external stakeholders were employing, as well as the results and these underlying questions, as to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island. These guide questions conducted face-to-face group interviews that took place according to the convenient time of the participants.

For validation purposes of the instrument, the researcher presented the draft of the interview part to the research adviser for initial comments and suggestions. Also, it was validated by at least five experts in the field, one Doctor graduate, two masters graduate, one District GAD Coordinator and one Municipal Health Officer, who also have experiences and concerns in the Gender and Development program implementation.

Data Gathering Procedure

Initially, the researcher conducted pre-interview first on the ground to address the difficulty of finding the right participants for the study. For almost four days, the researcher went back and forth to the whole island to ask different personnel from secondary schools as well as from external agencies if they were the concerned personnel on teenage pregnancies according to their role and also asked if they were implementing programs, activities, policies and other strategies to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancies in their district. After the right participants had been verified and selected, the researcher conducted the preliminary permit activity. As bound by rules of ethics, the researcher sent a letter of permission to the Schools Division Office, Schools’ Supervisors, and Mayors. After having the permits, the researcher started the distribution of letters, consent, permits, and guide questions in advance before interview day to the selected internal and external participants. These all were given from days and weeks before the actual interview. For the participants to walk through the process, the researcher scheduled a date for a face-to-face group interview. Since they had to be interviewed in a group, scheduling their availability has been so hard as they were very busy doing their job tasks, but also time came, and we all did it together. The group interview enabled the researcher and the participants to have an in-depth discussion regarding the matter being discussed and to gather the needed information without the high possibilities and threat of hypothetical answers from the interviewee.

Data Processing

To determine the strategies employed by the internal and external stakeholders, the problems they encountered, and how they resolved these problems to

address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island, the researcher employed thematic analysis to analyze the information gathered from the interview. After the participants of this study answered the guide questions during the interview, the researcher reviewed the video and used a speaker to hear the responses. The information gathered from here was transcribed bare hand (written) and typed to transfer in soft copy. These were printed, and the valuable statements were coded manually through a highlighter marker. After coding, axial coding was done to draw connections between the codes. The last one was selective coding to select one central category to connect all the codes from the analysis and come up with the essence of the research. (Babbie 388-391, 2016). Therefore, the process was done deductively, from general to specific, and this data analysis method was applied to all the variables in the problem statement.

Results and Discussion

Strategies Employed by the Internal and External Stakeholders to Address the Emerging Cases of Teenage Pregnancies in Alabat Island

Strategies employed by internal and external stakeholders discussed the underlying terms, these were the types of strategies employed, means of implementation, duration and other steps taken in the field.

Table 1.1. *Strategies Employed in Terms of Types of Strategies*

Strategies	Alabat, Quezon		T	Perez, Quezon		T	Quezon, Quezon		T	OT	R
	I	E		I	E		I	E			
Comprehensive Sex Education	4	2	6	4	2	6	5	1	6	18	1
Counseling	2	2	4	1	1	2	1	2	3	9	2
Youth Social Development	0	1	1	0	2	2	0	1	1	4	3
Awareness on rights and protection	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	4
No cellphone policy	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	6
Case Management	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	6
Parenthood Development	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	6

Legend: T- Total per Sub-Group; OT- Overall Total; R- Rank; I- Internal Stakeholders; E- External Stakeholders

The provided information presents the frequency distribution of internal and external stakeholders' responses regarding the strategies employed to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island. The data reveals the preferences and perspectives of these stakeholders in tackling this issue.

According to Table 1.1, the most commonly employed strategy to address teenage pregnancy is comprehensive sex education, which received a total of 18 responses. These responses were obtained from both internal and external stakeholders in different locations within Alabat Island. From Alabat, Quezon, there were 4 internal stakeholders and 2 external stakeholders, contributing to a total of 6 responses. In Perez, Quezon, there were 4 internal stakeholders and 2 external stakeholders, resulting in a total of 6 responses. Lastly, in Quezon, Quezon, there were 5 internal stakeholders and 1 external stakeholder, yielding a total of 6 responses. It is worth noting that the term "internal stakeholders" refers to individuals directly involved in the local community or organizations, such as teachers and school heads, while "external stakeholders" include parents, social workers, health employees, and other concerned groups.

Additionally, counseling was identified as a strategy employed by 9 respondents to address teenage pregnancy. The distribution of these respondents was as follows: 4 from Alabat, Quezon (2 internal stakeholders and 2 external stakeholders), 2 from Perez, Quezon (1 internal stakeholder and 1 external stakeholder), and 3 from Quezon, Quezon (1 internal stakeholder and 2 external stakeholders).

Furthermore, the data indicate that other strategies were also utilized by both internal and external stakeholders in addressing teenage pregnancy. These strategies include youth social development, which had 4 respondents across Alabat Island, awareness of rights and protection (2 respondents), parenthood development (1 respondent), case management (1 respondent), and the implementation of a no cellphone policy (1 respondent).

In summary, the gathered data from internal and external stakeholders in Alabat Island highlights comprehensive sex education as the most widely employed strategy to address teenage pregnancy. Counseling was also recognized as a significant approach. Moreover, there were additional strategies implemented, albeit with fewer responses, such as youth social development, awareness of rights and protection, parenthood development, case management, and the enforcement of a no cellphone policy. The findings suggest the importance of a multifaceted approach involving education, counseling, social development, and policy implementation to effectively address the issue of teenage pregnancy in the area.

The frequency distribution of stakeholders' responses regarding the strategies employed to address teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island has several implications.

Firstly, the overwhelming majority of stakeholders, both internal and external, emphasized the importance of comprehensive sex education as a strategy to tackle teenage pregnancy. This implies a recognition of the need for education and awareness regarding reproductive health, contraception, and responsible sexual behavior. It suggests that stakeholders believe that equipping adolescents with accurate and comprehensive information about sexuality can help reduce the incidence of teenage pregnancy.

Secondly, the significant number of respondents who identified counseling as a strategy indicates the recognition of the importance of emotional and psychological support for teenagers facing issues related to pregnancy. This implies that stakeholders acknowledge the complex factors influencing teenage pregnancy and the need for tailored support systems to address the emotional well-being of young individuals.

Furthermore, the diversity of strategies employed, including youth social development, awareness of rights and protection, parenthood development, case management, and the implementation of a no cell phone policy, suggests a comprehensive and holistic approach to tackling teenage pregnancy. This implies that stakeholders recognize the multi-faceted nature of the issue and the need to address it from various angles, encompassing social, educational, policy, and individual development aspects.

These implications highlight the significance of collaboration and coordination among different stakeholders, including educators, parents, healthcare professionals, social workers, and policymakers, to effectively address teenage pregnancy. The findings underscore the need for a comprehensive strategy that combines education, counseling, community support, and policy interventions to create a supportive environment for adolescents and reduce the occurrence of teenage pregnancy.

Overall, the implications of the frequency distribution of stakeholders' responses emphasize the importance of a multi-dimensional and collaborative approach that focuses on education, support, and policy implementation to address the complex issue of teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island.

According to Gregorio (2018) comprehensive sex

education plays a crucial role in the lives of high school learners, offering them essential knowledge and skills that are integral to their overall well-being and development. Firstly, comprehensive sex education provides accurate and reliable information about sexual health, reproduction, and relationships. It equips students with a comprehensive understanding of their bodies, sexual and reproductive processes, and the importance of practicing safe and consensual behavior. By providing scientifically accurate information, comprehensive sex education empowers high school learners to make informed decisions about their sexual health and relationships, reducing the likelihood of unplanned pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), and other potential risks.

Secondly, comprehensive sex education goes beyond the biological aspects and also addresses important social and emotional dimensions of sexuality. It promotes healthy attitudes, values, and communication skills related to relationships, consent, and respect. By fostering open and non-judgmental discussions about topics such as consent, boundaries, gender roles, and sexual diversity, comprehensive sex education helps to create a safe and inclusive environment for high school learners. It also enables them to develop crucial life skills, such as effective communication, decision-making, and critical thinking, which are essential for maintaining healthy relationships throughout their lives (Xavier, et al., 2018).

On the other hand, Epstein and colleagues (2018) said that counseling also plays a crucial role in reducing cases of teenage pregnancy by addressing the emotional, psychological, and social factors that contribute to risky sexual behaviors. Firstly, counseling provides a safe and confidential space for teenagers to express their thoughts, concerns, and fears related to relationships, sexuality, and pregnancy. It allows them to explore their feelings and beliefs, helping them develop a better understanding of themselves and their motivations. Through counseling, adolescents can gain insight into the underlying issues that may be influencing their choices, such as low self-esteem, peer pressure, or a lack of knowledge about contraception. By addressing these emotional and psychological factors, counseling helps teenagers make more informed and responsible decisions regarding their sexual behavior, reducing the likelihood of unplanned pregnancies.

Secondly, counseling equips teenagers with essential skills and strategies to navigate relationships and sexual situations effectively (Kost, et al., 2017). It provides education and guidance on healthy

relationship dynamics, communication skills, and assertiveness. Teenagers can learn how to set boundaries, negotiate consent, and make choices aligned with their values and goals. Additionally, counseling can provide information and access to contraception methods, ensuring that teenagers are aware of and have the resources to protect themselves against unintended pregnancies. By empowering teenagers with the necessary knowledge and skills, counseling helps them build resilience, make informed decisions, and develop healthy behaviors, all of which contribute to reducing the incidence of teenage pregnancy.

In summary, comprehensive sex education is of paramount importance for high school learners. It provides accurate information, equips them with essential skills, and promotes healthy attitudes and behaviors. By offering a holistic approach to sexuality education, comprehensive sex education empowers young individuals to make responsible choices, promotes their sexual health and well-being, and contributes to the reduction of teenage pregnancies, STIs, and other potential risks. Thus, counseling plays a vital role in reducing cases of teenage pregnancy by addressing the emotional, psychological, and social factors that contribute to risky sexual behaviors. It provides a supportive environment for teenagers to explore their thoughts and feelings, equips them with essential skills and knowledge, and helps them develop healthy relationships and decision-making abilities (Vaughan et al., 2018). By addressing the underlying issues and promoting responsible behavior, counseling serves as a valuable tool in preventing teenage pregnancies and supporting the overall well-being of adolescents.

Table 1.2. *Strategies Employed in Terms of Means or Ways of Implementation*

Means/ Ways	Alabat, Quezon		Perez, Quezon		Quezon, Quezon		OT	R			
	I	E	I	E	I	E					
Through giving brochures	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	9.5		
Through reminding co-workers	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	9.5		
Integration to the discussion	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	9.5		
Through parent-teacher conference	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	5		
Through group face-to-face session with teenagers	1	0	1	2	0	2	0	1	4	3	
Through one-on-one face-to-face session with teenagers	1	3	4	1	2	3	1	3	4	11	1
Through symposium	0	2	2	1	2	3	3	0	3	8	2
Through seminars and sports activity	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	9.5
Home visitation	0	2	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	3	4
Collaboration with concerned personnel	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	9.5
Through Phases or steps	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	9.5
Through class visitation	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	9.5
Through policy/regulation	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	9.5

Legend: T- Total per Sub-Group; OT- Overall Total; R- Rank; I- Internal Stakeholders; E- External Stakeholders

Table 1.2 provides a comprehensive overview of the means or ways utilized by respondents to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island. The data highlights various strategies employed by both internal and external stakeholders, shedding light on the diverse approaches taken to tackle this issue.

The most commonly employed means or way to address teenage pregnancy, as indicated by the respondents, is through one-on-one face-to-face sessions with teenagers, which received a total of 11 responses. This strategy emphasizes the importance of direct interaction and personalized communication with adolescents. It allows stakeholders to engage in open and confidential discussions, providing guidance, support, and information tailored to individual needs. The distribution of responses across different locations indicates a widespread adoption of this approach, with stakeholders from Alabat, Quezon, Perez, Quezon, and Quezon, Quezon all employing one-on-one face-to-face sessions. Notably, this strategy was more commonly utilized by external stakeholders, suggesting their active involvement in directly addressing teenage pregnancy.

Another prominent means or way used by stakeholders is through symposiums, which garnered 8 responses. Symposia provide a platform for disseminating information, raising awareness, and fostering discussions on teenage pregnancy among a larger audience. The responses indicate that stakeholders from Alabat, Quezon, Perez, Quezon, and Quezon, Quezon have organized symposiums as part of their efforts to address the issue. The inclusion of both internal and external stakeholders in this strategy suggests a collaborative approach, bringing together different perspectives and expertise to create a comprehensive dialogue on teenage pregnancy.

Furthermore, the data reveals a range of other means or ways employed by stakeholders to address teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island. These include brochure dissemination, reminding co-workers, integration of subject matter, parent-teacher conferences, group face-to-face sessions with teenagers, seminars, sports activities, home visitation, collaboration with concerned personnel, phased approaches by social workers, class visitation, and the implementation of policies or regulations. This comprehensive list demonstrates the multifaceted and proactive nature of the strategies implemented. It reflects the recognition that addressing teenage pregnancy requires a holistic approach that encompasses education, awareness,

support networks, community involvement, and policy frameworks.

In summary, the implications derived from the frequency distribution of means or ways to address teenage pregnancy highlight the significance of personalized support and community engagement. The emphasis on one-on-one face-to-face sessions underscores the importance of tailored guidance for teenagers, taking into account their unique needs and circumstances. The utilization of symposiums reflects a collective effort to raise awareness and foster community involvement in addressing teenage pregnancy. These implications emphasize the need for comprehensive strategies that combine individualized support, community engagement, and information dissemination to effectively address the issue of teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island.

Grugi (2018) emphasized on the individual face-to-face conferences with students. It plays a crucial role in addressing teenage pregnancy by providing tailored support, guidance, and education. These conferences offer a personalized approach that allows educators, counselors, or healthcare professionals to have direct and private conversations with students about their specific concerns and questions regarding teenage pregnancy. By engaging in one-on-one discussions, professionals can understand the unique circumstances of each student and provide targeted support to address their individual needs.

According to Borrero and colleagues (2019), one of the key benefits of individual face-to-face conferences is the establishment of trust and open communication. Students often feel more comfortable discussing sensitive topics such as teenage pregnancy in a private setting where they can openly express their thoughts and concerns. By creating a safe and confidential environment, professionals can build trust with students, fostering a supportive relationship. This trust is crucial for students to feel empowered to share their experiences, seek guidance, and ask questions without fear of judgment or stigma. Through open communication, professionals can address any misconceptions, provide accurate information about reproductive health and contraception, and offer guidance on making informed decisions.

Moreover, individual face-to-face conferences allow professionals to address the unique needs and circumstances of each student. By tailoring the support to the individual, professionals can provide personalized guidance on topics such as pregnancy prevention, healthy relationships, and emotional well-

being. They can also identify any underlying issues that may contribute to the risk of teenage pregnancy, such as low self-esteem, peer pressure, or a lack of access to healthcare and contraception (Carter et al., 2017). By addressing these factors and connecting students with appropriate resources and services, professionals can effectively support students in making responsible choices and reducing the incidence of teenage pregnancy.

Table 1.3. *Strategies Employed in terms of Frequency of Implementation*

Duration of Programs	Alabat,		Perez,		Quezon,		T	OT	R		
	I	E	I	E	I	E					
Done once in a year	3	1	4	3	1	4	4	2	6	14	2
Done always	2	3	5	1	5	6	2	3	5	16	1
Done quarterly	2	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	3	3
Done sometimes	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	4

Legend: T- Total per Sub-Group; OT- Overall Total; R- Rank; I- Internal Stakeholders; E- External Stakeholders

Table 1.3 shows the frequency distribution of the internal and external stakeholders as to the duration of programs to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island.

Table 1.3 presents the frequency distribution of internal and external stakeholders in relation to the duration of programs implemented to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island. The data reveals that the majority of stakeholders opt for always implementation of programs, indicating a sustained and continuous effort to address teenage pregnancy. Specifically, 16 responses across different locations, such as Alabat, Quezon, Perez, Quezon, and Quezon, Quezon, emphasized the importance of always ongoing programs. Notably, external stakeholders played a significant role in implementing these programs as always, indicating their commitment to providing continuous support and resources to address teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island.

In contrast, there were 14 responses indicated that stakeholders implement programs once a year. This approach was predominantly observed among internal stakeholders, particularly teachers. These annual programs are likely designed to coincide with the academic calendar, offering targeted interventions and educational initiatives within a specific timeframe. While they may have a less frequency compared to frequency of always in the implementation, they still serve as valuable platforms for raising awareness, providing information, and engaging with adolescents to prevent teenage pregnancy. The involvement of internal stakeholders, particularly teachers, highlights

the crucial role of educational institutions in addressing this issue and equipping students with essential knowledge and skills.

Furthermore, a subset of internal and external stakeholders implemented programs on a quarterly basis. This flexible approach allows for regular check-ins, assessments, and adjustments to strategies based on the evolving needs and challenges related to teenage pregnancy. Quarterly programs provide opportunities for stakeholders to evaluate the effectiveness of their interventions and make necessary adaptations to ensure their relevance and impact.

This implied that the diversity in the frequency of programs implemented by stakeholders to address teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island. The prevalence of always implementation of programs indicates a recognition of the long-term commitment required to tackle this issue. However, the presence of annual programs highlights the role of internal stakeholders, particularly teachers, in providing targeted interventions within the school setting. Lastly, the availability of quarterly programs showcases the importance of adaptability and periodic evaluations to ensure the effectiveness of prevention efforts. By considering these different approaches, stakeholders can tailor their programs to the unique needs of the community, optimize resource allocation, and maximize the impact of their initiatives in reducing teenage pregnancy rates in Alabat Island.

The data shows that a significant number of stakeholders have opted the implementation programs as always to address teenage pregnancy. This approach, supported by both internal and external stakeholders, reflects a commitment to continuous engagement and support for adolescents throughout the year. Differently, the implementation of programs as always allows for sustained education, intervention, and resources, enabling stakeholders to address the multifaceted aspects of teenage pregnancy prevention. Scholars have recognized the value of always implementation of programs, emphasizing their ability to provide ongoing support, reinforce key messages, and establish long-term behavior change among adolescents (Roberts et al., 2019). In relation, the continuous nature of always implementation of programs ensures that adolescents receive consistent guidance, access to resources, and opportunities for reinforcement, ultimately contributing to a comprehensive and holistic approach to tackling teenage pregnancy.

In contrast, a considerable number of stakeholders

have chosen to implement programs once a year. This approach, primarily adopted by internal stakeholders such as teachers, suggests the recognition of the significance of targeted interventions delivered on an annual basis. While these programs may have a more limited frequency, they offer a focused opportunity to educate and raise awareness among adolescents. Annual programs provide a platform for internal stakeholders to deliver comprehensive sexuality education, update students on relevant information, and engage in open dialogue about teenage pregnancy prevention. Although they may not provide the same level of sustained support as always implementation of programs, annual interventions are still valuable in equipping students with essential knowledge and skills to make informed decisions (Davis & Thompson, 2017). Furthermore, the involvement of internal stakeholders, particularly teachers, underscores the role of educational institutions in addressing teenage pregnancy and highlights their responsibility in providing relevant and timely guidance.

The data also indicate that some stakeholders have implemented programs on a quarterly basis. Quarterly programs offer a balance between regular engagement and flexibility in program duration. This approach allows stakeholders to address emerging needs, reassess strategies, and provide consistent check-ins with adolescents. The quarterly model enables stakeholders to maintain a level of ongoing support and education while allowing for periodic evaluations and adjustments. By adopting a quarterly program duration, stakeholders can address the dynamic nature of teenage pregnancy prevention, respond to evolving challenges, and ensure the relevance and effectiveness of their interventions (Phuhongsai, 2018).

Table 1.4. *Strategies Employed in terms of Other Action Taken*

Other Steps Taken	Alabat, Quezon		Perez, Quezon		Quezon, Quezon		T	OT	R		
	n		T		T						
	I	E	I	E	I	E					
Include the Teenage Pregnancy Awareness to AIP and SIP	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	6
Following mandates	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	4
Doing extra effort to promote the Teenage Pregnancy Awareness such as follow-ups and visitation	3	2	5	3	3	6	1	3	4	15	1
Strengthening partnerships with parents	1	2	3	2	1	3	0	1	1	7	2
Strengthening spiritual aspect	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	6
Having strict implementation Teenage Pregnancy Awareness	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	6
Strengthening partnerships with stakeholders	1	1	2	0	2	2	0	1	1	5	3

Legend: T- Total per Sub-Group; OT-Overall-Total; R- Rank; I- Internal Stakeholders; E- External Stakeholders

Table 1.4 shows the frequency distribution of the respondents as to other actions taken to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancy in Alabat Island. The study found that respondents went above and above to encourage teenage pregnancy awareness, including follow-ups, visits, monitoring, giving financial, and integration in ICT lesson, with a total of 16 responses. These were from Alabat, Quezon, with three internal stakeholders and two external stakeholders, for a total of five responses. Perez, Quezon has three internal and three external stakeholders, for a total of six responses, and Quezon, Quezon has one internal and three external stakeholders, for a total of four responses. The survey also discovered that the majority of the stakeholders are taking further actions to address the growing cases of adolescent pregnancy in Alabat Island.

On the other hand, some of the respondents include programs to raise awareness of their annual implementation plan (AIP) and school improvement plan (SIP), following mandates, strengthening parents' partnership, strengthening partnerships with stakeholders, strengthening spiritual aspects, and strict implementation of the teenage pregnancy awareness program. The findings revealed valuable insights into the efforts made by stakeholders in each location.

In Alabat, Quezon, the study recorded a total of 3 responses, indicating a significant level of engagement from parents. Among these responses were one internal stakeholder and two external stakeholders. The study mentioned follow-ups and visits as actions undertaken, demonstrating a proactive approach to raising awareness about teenage pregnancy. Although the specifics of these actions were not elaborated upon, the overall impression is that stakeholders in Alabat, Quezon are actively involved in addressing this issue.

Moving to Perez, Quezon, the study identified a total of 12 respondents. This location showcased an equal distribution of internal and external stakeholders, with six from each category. This balance suggests collaborative efforts between the local community and external entities to address teenage pregnancy awareness. Perez showed that their additional actions were doing home visitations, follow and others, followed by strengthening relationships with the parents, the other themes got fewer responses. The data from Perez have shown that they were not neglecting their duty as agent of the community and raising awareness on teenage pregnancy despite challenges they have on their way.

Lastly, Quezon, Quezon had 11 stakeholders who responded to the survey. Among them, 6 were internal stakeholder from the local community, while the remaining six were external stakeholders. The presence of external stakeholders indicates that support is being extended from organizations or individuals outside of the immediate area. Although the number of stakeholders in Quezon, Quezon was relatively small compared to the other locations, their involvement suggests a commitment to addressing the issue of adolescent pregnancy. They also doing extra effort to bring information and services to the teenagers and community, however although the remaining actions got fewer response, they were sure that they are exerting their very best just to lessen the number of teenage pregnancy cases.

Previous studies on teenage pregnancy awareness have highlighted the importance of stakeholder engagement and collaborative efforts in addressing this issue effectively. The findings of the current study align with these previous studies, as they indicate active involvement and engagement from both internal and external stakeholders in all three municipalities.

The study's emphasis on follow-ups and visits as actions taken by stakeholders reflects a proactive approach that has been found to be effective in previous research. Follow-ups and visits allow for continued support, counseling, and educational interventions, which have shown to positively impact teenage pregnancy prevention efforts (Nabugoomu, 2020).

Moreover, the study's identification of a higher number of stakeholders and responses in Alabat, Quezon compared to Perez, Quezon, and Quezon, Quezon may indicate varying levels of awareness and engagement across different regions. This finding aligns with previous studies that have shown regional disparities in teenage pregnancy rates and awareness programs. It underscores the importance of tailoring interventions and initiatives to specific local contexts (Finley et al., 2017).

Additionally, the involvement of external stakeholders in all three locations suggests the recognition of the need for a multi-sectoral approach to address teenage pregnancy. Previous studies have emphasized the significance of collaborations between local communities, healthcare providers, educational institutions, and other organizations to create a comprehensive support system for young people (Gcelu, 2019).

Results of Strategies Employed by the Internal and External Stakeholders in Alabat Island

The results of the study discussed the following, these were the results of the strategies as decreasing or increasing, as well as the factors affecting the implementation, coping mechanism and effects of the programs.

Table 2.1. Results of the Strategies Employed in Terms of Number of Cases in the Year 2021 and 2022

Municipality	Strategies	Year 2021	Year 2022	Remarks
Alabat	Comprehensive Sex Education			
	Counseling	3	12	Increased
Perez	Youth Social Development			
	Awareness on rights and protection			
	Case Management			
	Comprehensive Sex Education	3	6	Increased
	Youth Social Development			
	Awareness on rights and protection			
	No cellphone Policy			
	Youth Social Development			

Table 2.1 shows the frequency distribution of the internal and external stakeholders as to the results of the strategies employed to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island.

The given research provides information about the number of teenage pregnancies in three different municipalities in Alabat Island, specifically Alabat, Perez, and Quezon. It highlights the contrasting trends in the occurrence of teenage pregnancies despite the implementation of various interventions aimed at addressing the issue.

In Alabat, Quezon, the research reveals that there were three cases of teenage pregnancies in the year 2021. However, the number increased to 12 in the following year, resulting in a total of 15 cases over the span of two consecutive years. Despite the presence of comprehensive sex education in schools, counseling services, youth social development programs, awareness campaigns on rights and protection, and community intervention through case management, the rise in teenage pregnancies indicates that these measures have not been successful in effectively mitigating the issue in Alabat.

On the other hand, in Perez, Quezon, the research reports three cases of teenage pregnancies in 2021. The number of cases increased to six in 2022, resulting in a total of nine cases over the two-year period. The study suggests that the interventions in Perez, such as comprehensive sex education, counseling, youth social development initiatives, and awareness campaigns, coupled with a no cellphone policy in schools and communities, have also not proven to be entirely effective in reducing teenage pregnancies.

In the case of Quezon, Quezon, the research indicates that the key respondents did not provide their responses concerning teenage pregnancies in their municipality. Therefore, it is not possible to draw any conclusions about the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of interventions in mitigating teenage pregnancies in that specific area.

Overall, the research highlights the persistent challenge of teenage pregnancies in these municipalities despite the implementation of various measures. It suggests that additional efforts or alternative strategies may be necessary to address the underlying factors contributing to the issue. Further analysis and investigation are required to understand the specific reasons behind the ineffectiveness of the implemented interventions and to develop more targeted and impactful approaches in reducing teenage pregnancies in these areas.

The results of the research on teenage pregnancies in the municipalities of Alabat, Perez, and Quezon in Quezon Province have significant implications. Firstly, it suggests that the current interventions, including comprehensive sex education, counseling services, youth social development programs, and awareness campaigns, have not been successful in effectively reducing the number of teenage pregnancies. This calls for a critical evaluation of these interventions to identify gaps and areas for improvement. Tailored approaches that consider the unique socio-cultural, economic, and educational contexts of each community should be developed to address the issue more effectively.

Secondly, the findings highlight the importance of regularly evaluating the outcomes of implemented interventions. Monitoring and assessing the effectiveness of programs and strategies can help identify what works and what does not, allowing for timely adjustments and improvements. Furthermore, it emphasizes the need to address underlying factors that contribute to teenage pregnancies, such as socio-economic disparities, limited access to reproductive

healthcare, cultural norms, and societal attitudes towards sexuality. Holistic solutions should be developed that take these factors into account to address the root causes of the issue.

Lastly, the research underscores the significance of collaboration and coordination among stakeholders involved in addressing teenage pregnancies. Schools, healthcare providers, community organizations, parents, and policymakers need to work together, sharing knowledge, resources, and best practices to develop comprehensive and effective strategies. Evidence-based approaches should be prioritized, ensuring that decision-making and intervention planning are guided by sound research and data analysis. Additionally, further research is needed to gain a deeper understanding of the challenges and factors specific to each area, enabling the development of targeted interventions and the identification of emerging trends.

The previous discussion on the importance of implementing comprehensive sex education in schools and communities directly relates to the issue of teenage pregnancies. Teenage pregnancies often occur due to a lack of information, inadequate access to contraception, limited understanding of reproductive health, and societal norms that may perpetuate risky sexual behaviors. Comprehensive sex education addresses these factors and aims to prevent teenage pregnancies through various means (Halonon, 2017).

According to Phuhongsai (2018), by providing accurate and evidence-based information about sexual health, comprehensive sex education equips young individuals with the knowledge they need to understand the potential consequences of engaging in sexual activities. It educates them about the importance of contraception, STI prevention, and responsible sexual behavior, helping to reduce the risk of unintended pregnancies.

Empowering informed decision-making is another critical aspect of comprehensive sex education. By teaching young people about consent, healthy relationships, and communication skills, comprehensive sex education encourages them to make choices based on their own desires and boundaries. This can help prevent situations where teenage pregnancies may arise from coercive or non-consensual sexual encounters (Gavin et al., 2016).

Harold (2018) said that promoting healthy relationships through comprehensive sex education is also vital in addressing teenage pregnancies. By emphasizing mutual respect, communication, and

consent, comprehensive sex education equips young individuals with the tools to develop and maintain healthy relationships. This can contribute to a reduction in risky sexual behaviors and unplanned pregnancies that may result from unhealthy or abusive relationships. Furthermore, comprehensive sex education addresses gender and social norms that contribute to the vulnerability of young individuals. By challenging harmful stereotypes and promoting gender equality, comprehensive sex education aims to empower young people to make decisions based on their own needs and aspirations, rather than conforming to societal expectations. This can help reduce the pressure and influence that traditional gender roles may have on young individuals' sexual behavior and choices.

Involving parents and communities in comprehensive sex education is crucial in providing a supportive environment for young individuals (Omeje, 2019). By engaging parents, comprehensive sex education promotes open communication and shared responsibility in educating young people about sexual health. It helps parents understand the importance of providing accurate information, supporting their children's decision-making, and creating a safe space for discussing sensitive topics. This involvement can contribute to a reduction in teenage pregnancies by fostering an atmosphere of understanding, guidance, and support.

Table 2.2. Results of Strategies Employed in Terms of Problems encountered in the Implementation

Factors Affecting the Implementation of Strategies	Alabat, Quezon		T	Perez, Quezon		T	Quezon, Quezon		OT	R
	I	E		I	E		I	E		
Lack of budget allocation to the program	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	10
Lack of cooperation of the teenagers/ youth	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	9
Lack of willingness and interest of the youth to the program	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	3	3	7
Lack of parental guidance and proper supervision	3	1	4	3	0	3	0	4	4	11
Lack of parents' participation and support to the program	3	1	4	0	1	1	2	1	3	8
Irresponsible use of technology and social media of teenagers	1	1	2	4	2	6	0	1	1	9
Unresponsive behavior and attitude of teenagers toward the program	2	3	5	1	1	2	0	0	0	7
Peer influence	4	0	4	1	0	1	0	1	1	6
Lack of participation in school-initiated sex education	1	2	3	1	1	2	1	2	3	7
Burden of other additional workloads	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	3

Legend: T- Total per Sub-Group; OT- Overall Total; R- Rank; I- Internal Stakeholders; E- External Stakeholders

Table 2.2 shows the frequency distribution of the internal and external stakeholders as to the problems encountered in the implementation of strategies to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancies in

Alabat Island.

According to Table 2.2, the lack of parental guidance and support emerges as a significant problem encountered in the implementation of strategies to address teenage pregnancies, with a total of 11 responses indicating this issue. Among these responses, there were 4 cases reported in Alabat, Quezon, 3 cases in Perez, Quezon, and 4 cases in Quezon, Quezon. This highlights the critical role of parents in supporting the strategies and interventions aimed at reducing teenage pregnancies. The lack of parental guidance and support can hinder the effectiveness of these programs, potentially leading to an increase in teenage pregnancy rates within schools and communities.

In addition to the lack of parental support, the irresponsible use of technology and social media by teenagers also emerges as a prominent factor affecting the implementation of strategies. The data reveals that 2 cases in Alabat, Quezon, 6 cases in Perez, Quezon, and 1 case in Quezon, Quezon were attributed to this issue. The improper and reckless use of technology and social media platforms can expose teenagers to explicit content, encourage risky behaviors, and facilitate the development of inappropriate relationships. These factors can contribute to early and unintended pregnancies among teenagers, emphasizing the need for comprehensive education and awareness programs to address this concern.

Furthermore, the lack of parents' participation and support for the program is highlighted as another significant problem encountered in the failure of intervention programs aimed at decreasing teenage pregnancy rates. The input from 8 respondents across different municipalities of Alabat Island underscores the importance of engaging parents in initiatives that address teenage pregnancies. Parental involvement plays a crucial role in reinforcing the messages and lessons learned through intervention programs, as parents can provide guidance, support, and a nurturing environment that complements the efforts made within educational institutions and the broader community.

To overcome these challenges, it is crucial to develop comprehensive strategies that involve and educate parents on the importance of their active participation and support in addressing teenage pregnancies. Collaborative efforts between schools, community organizations, and parents can facilitate effective communication, promote positive parenting practices, and strengthen the implementation of interventions. Additionally, raising awareness about responsible

technology use, providing guidance on internet safety, and fostering digital literacy among teenagers can help mitigate the negative impact of technology and social media on teenage pregnancy rates.

The implications of the results presented in Table 2.2 regarding teenage pregnancies are significant and provide valuable insights for addressing this issue effectively. Firstly, the finding that the lack of parental guidance and support is a major problem encountered affecting the implementation of strategies highlights the crucial role parents play in preventing teenage pregnancies. It underscores the need for targeted interventions that engage parents and provide them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and support to actively participate in addressing this issue. By involving parents, educators, and community stakeholders in comprehensive sex education programs and promoting open communication, strategies can be developed to bridge the gap and ensure consistent guidance and support for teenagers, thus reducing the risk of early pregnancies.

Secondly, the impact of the irresponsible use of technology and social media on teenage pregnancies calls for a multi-faceted approach. It is crucial to educate teenagers about responsible technology use, digital citizenship, and online safety. Implementing awareness campaigns, workshops, and school programs that address the risks and consequences of inappropriate online behavior can empower teenagers to make informed choices and navigate the digital world responsibly. Additionally, involving parents in these initiatives can reinforce positive online behaviors and promote a safer online environment for young individuals.

Furthermore, the lack of parents' participation in intervention programs indicates the importance of engaging and involving parents from the early stages of program development. Creating awareness among parents about the significance of their participation and encouraging their active involvement can enhance the effectiveness of strategies aimed at preventing teenage pregnancies. Schools, community organizations, and healthcare providers can collaborate to offer parenting workshops, support groups, and resources that equip parents with the knowledge and skills to address issues related to adolescent sexual health, fostering a supportive and informed environment.

According to Kost and colleagues (2017), parental guidance and proper support are of utmost importance in preventing early or teenage pregnancies. Firstly, through comprehensive education and open

communication, parents can equip their children with accurate information and promote healthy attitudes towards sexuality. By engaging in ongoing conversations about sexual health, relationships, and responsible behavior, parents can empower their children to make informed choices and understand the potential consequences of early sexual activities. Open dialogue allows parents to dispel myths and misconceptions, ensuring that their children have a solid foundation of knowledge to make informed decisions.

Secondly, UNESCO (2018) reiterated that setting clear boundaries and expectations is crucial in preventing early pregnancies. When parents communicate their values, expectations, and guidelines to their children, they provide them with a framework for responsible behavior. By establishing boundaries around relationships and sexual activities, parents can help their children develop a strong sense of self-worth and self-respect. This, in turn, can prevent teenagers from engaging in risky behaviors, such as unprotected sex or entering into unhealthy relationships, that may lead to early pregnancies. Parental involvement in setting boundaries provides teenagers with guidance and support, helping them navigate peer pressure and make responsible decisions.

Lastly, Stanger-Hall & Hall (2017) noted that parental support plays a significant role in fostering emotional well-being and positive role modeling. By creating a nurturing and supportive environment, parents provide teenagers with the emotional support they need to navigate the challenges of adolescence. When teenagers feel supported and valued by their parents, they are more likely to seek guidance and support from them when facing relationship or sexual health issues. Additionally, positive parental role modeling, such as displaying healthy relationships, mutual respect, and responsible behavior, can have a profound impact on teenagers' choices. When parents model healthy behaviors, they provide their children with examples to follow and guide them toward making responsible decisions regarding their sexual health.

Table 2.3. Results of Strategies Employed in Terms of Coping Mechanism to Address problems encountered in the implementation

Coping Mechanism to Address Factors Affecting the Implementation of Strategies	Alabat, Quezon			Perez, Quezon			Quezon, Quezon			OT	R
	I	E	T	I	E	T	I	E	T		
Realignment of budget from AIP	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	8.5
Providing handouts and brochure relative to teenage pregnancy	1	1	2	2	0	2	0	1	1	5	2.5
Giving more encouragement and meaningful activities	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	3	5.5
Doing home visitations and follow-ups	1	3	4	3	1	4	0	1	1	9	1
Giving rewards to increase parents' participation	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	5.5
Teaching proper technology and social media among teenagers	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	2	3	5.5
Provide real life examples about the results of teenage pregnancies	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	2	8.5
Provide collaborative activities	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	5.5
Encourage the learners to attend to the discussion about sex education	2	2	4	1	0	1	0	0	0	5	2.5

Legend: T- Total per Sub-Group; OT-Overall Total; R- Rank; I- Internal Stakeholders; E- External Stakeholders

Table 2.3 shows the frequency distribution of the internal and external stakeholders as to the coping mechanism to address the factors affecting the implementation of strategies to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island.

Table 2.3 reveals that home visitations and follow-ups are considered one of the primary coping strategies employed by internal and external stakeholders to address the factors influencing the implementation of strategies related to teenage pregnancies. This coping mechanism received a total response of 9, with 4 respondents from Alabat, Quezon, 3 respondents from Perez, Quezon, and 1 respondent from Quezon, Quezon. The significance of home visitations and follow-ups lies in their ability to provide personalized support, guidance, and monitoring to teenagers and their families, which can contribute to the prevention of teenage pregnancies.

Home visitations and follow-ups allow stakeholders to establish direct contact with teenagers and their families in their own environment. This approach provides a deeper understanding of the family dynamics, living conditions, and individual circumstances that may contribute to teenage pregnancies. By visiting homes and conducting follow-up visits, stakeholders can identify and address specific challenges, provide tailored information, and offer

support systems that meet the unique needs of each teenager. This personalized approach enhances the effectiveness of interventions by fostering trust, strengthening relationships, and creating a supportive network for teenagers and their families.

The results of the study indicate that home visitations and follow-ups are primary coping strategies employed by both internal and external stakeholders to address factors influencing the implementation of strategies related to teenage pregnancies. These strategies received a positive response from the participants, with a total of 9 respondents acknowledging their significance. The respondents were distributed across different locations, with the majority from Alabat and Perez, Quezon.

The significance of home visitations and follow-ups lies in their ability to provide personalized support, guidance, and monitoring to teenagers and their families, which can contribute to the prevention of teenage pregnancies. By establishing direct contact with teenagers and their families in their own environment, stakeholders gain a deeper understanding of the family dynamics, living conditions, and individual circumstances that may contribute to teenage pregnancies. This understanding allows stakeholders to identify and address specific challenges, provide tailored information, and offer support systems that meet the unique needs of each teenager.

Home visitations and follow-ups also facilitate continuous monitoring and evaluation of the implemented strategies (Littell and Wynn, 2017). By regularly visiting teenagers and their families, stakeholders can assess the progress, identify any gaps or areas that require additional support, and modify interventions accordingly. This iterative process ensures that the strategies remain relevant and effective in addressing the factors influencing teenage pregnancies.

Furthermore, home visitations and follow-ups serve as a means of continuous monitoring and evaluation of the implemented strategies. By regularly visiting teenagers and their families, stakeholders can assess the progress, identify any gaps or areas that require additional support, and modify interventions accordingly. This iterative process allows for the adaptation and improvement of strategies over time, ensuring their relevance and effectiveness in addressing the factors influencing teenage pregnancies (Yussif et al., 2017).

Table 2.4. Results of Strategies Employed in Terms of Effects of Teenage Pregnancy Programs

Effects of Teenage Pregnancy Programs	Alabat,		Perez,		Quezon,		T	OT	R		
	I	E	I	E	I	E					
Increasing of level of awareness on the effects of teenage pregnancy	1	1	2	1	0	1	0	1	1	4	4
Lowering the rates of teenage pregnancy	3	3	6	2	4	6	1	4	5	17	1
Developing happy life and community	2	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	2	7	2.5
Decrease the number of drop-out from schools	1	2	3	1	1	2	1	1	2	7	2.5

Legend: T- Total per Sub-Group; OT- Overall Total; R- Rank; I- Internal Stakeholders; E- External Stakeholders

Table 2.4 shows the frequency distribution of the internal and external stakeholders as to the effects of teenage pregnancy programs to address the emerging cases of teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island.

According to Table 2.4, the implemented programs by both internal and external stakeholders have shown promising results in lowering the rates of teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island. The table indicates that 17 respondents, distributed across different locations, acknowledged the positive impact of these programs. The majority of respondents were from Alabat and Perez, Quezon, with additional responses from Quezon, Quezon.

The fact that the respondents believe that the implementation of programs help decrease the number of teenage pregnancies is significant. It suggests that the efforts made by stakeholders to address this issue through various programs and interventions are being recognized and appreciated. The respondents' positive perception indicates that these programs have the potential to make a difference in reducing teenage pregnancies.

Furthermore, it is noteworthy that 7 respondents mentioned that the implemented programs contribute to the development of a happy life and community. This finding suggests that these programs not only focus on preventing teenage pregnancies but also aim to create a positive and supportive environment for teenagers. By promoting happiness and community development, the programs address broader aspects of well-being and social cohesion.

In addition, 7 respondents expressed that the implemented programs help decrease the number of dropouts in school. This finding highlights the potential of these programs to address one of the consequences of teenage pregnancies, which is often the disruption of education. By providing support and

resources to teenagers, the programs aim to enable them to continue their education and pursue a brighter future.

The implications of the findings from Table 2.4 are twofold: first, the implemented programs by internal and external stakeholders have the potential to significantly reduce the rates of teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island. The positive responses from the respondents indicate that these programs are effective in addressing the underlying factors contributing to teenage pregnancies and fostering a supportive environment for teenagers. Second, the programs have broader benefits beyond pregnancy prevention, as they contribute to the development of a happy life, community well-being, and a decrease in school dropouts. This suggests that a comprehensive approach that considers the holistic needs of teenagers can yield positive outcomes in multiple domains of their lives. These implications highlight the importance of continued investment in and support for such programs to create lasting change and improve the overall well-being of teenagers in the community.

Jemmott (2016) showed that the teenage pregnancy program plays a crucial role in mitigating cases of early teenage pregnancy through its comprehensive approach. Firstly, the program focuses on providing accurate and age-appropriate information about sexual and reproductive health to teenagers. By equipping them with knowledge about contraception, sexually transmitted infections, and healthy relationships, the program empowers teenagers to make informed decisions and practice safe sexual behavior. This education component helps to prevent unintended pregnancies by ensuring that teenagers have the necessary information to protect themselves and make responsible choices.

Secondly, the teenage pregnancy program emphasizes the importance of access to reproductive health services. It ensures that teenagers have easy and confidential access to reproductive healthcare, including contraceptives, regular check-ups, and counseling services (Rosenberg et al., 2016). By removing barriers to healthcare, such as cost, stigma, and lack of awareness, the program enables teenagers to seek timely and appropriate care when needed. This accessibility to reproductive health services promotes early detection and intervention, reducing the risk of early teenage pregnancies and their associated complications.

Furthermore, Araniago (2019) noted that the teenage pregnancy program addresses the psychosocial aspects

of teenage pregnancy. It offers support systems such as counseling, peer education, and mentorship programs to help teenagers navigate the challenges they may face. By providing emotional support, guidance, and positive role models, the program helps teenagers build resilience, self-esteem, and the skills necessary to make healthy life choices. This holistic approach acknowledges the complex factors that contribute to early teenage pregnancy and aims to address them comprehensively, creating a supportive environment that encourages teenagers to delay parenthood and focus on their personal growth and development.

On the Localized Gender and Development (GAD) Intervention Program Derived from the Study

Based on the results of the study, a localized Gender and Development (GAD) program could be developed to address the factors influencing teenage pregnancies in the specific context of the study area. The program could focus on the following key components:

1. **Comprehensive Sexuality Education:** Implement a targeted and age-appropriate comprehensive sexuality education curriculum in schools and community settings. This curriculum should provide accurate information on sexual and reproductive health, healthy relationships, gender equality, and consent. It should also address the specific challenges and cultural factors related to teenage pregnancies in the local context.

2. **Community Engagement and Stakeholder Collaboration:** Establish partnerships with local communities, parents, educators, healthcare providers, and other relevant stakeholders. Engage them in the development and implementation of the program to ensure its relevance and effectiveness. This collaboration can include organizing community forums, workshops, and awareness campaigns to raise awareness about teenage pregnancy prevention and promote community support.

3. **Accessible Reproductive Health Services:** Improve access to youth-friendly reproductive health services by working closely with local healthcare providers. This can involve setting up dedicated adolescent-friendly clinics, ensuring the availability of contraceptives, promoting regular check-ups, and providing counseling services. It is essential to address any barriers that may prevent teenagers from seeking and utilizing reproductive health services, such as stigma, confidentiality concerns, or financial constraints.

4. **Mentorship and Peer Support:** Establish mentorship and peer support programs that connect teenagers with positive role models and peers who can provide guidance and support. These programs can involve trained mentors who offer one-on-one guidance, group activities that promote positive social interactions, and platforms for open discussions on topics related to sexuality, relationships, and life skills. Peer educators can also be trained to disseminate accurate information and act as resources for their peers.

5. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Implement a robust monitoring and evaluation system to continuously assess the effectiveness of the program. This can include tracking the rates of teenage pregnancies, dropout rates, and the utilization of reproductive health services. Regular evaluations should be conducted to identify any gaps or areas for improvement, allowing for adjustments and modifications to enhance the program's impact.

By developing a localized GAD program based on the study's findings, the specific needs and challenges related to teenage pregnancies in the area can be addressed effectively. This program should be contextually tailored, involving active community participation and collaboration with stakeholders to ensure its success and sustainability.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were obtained:

1. The study conducted in Alabat, Perez, and Quezon, Quezon, provides important insights into the perceptions of stakeholders regarding interventions aimed at addressing teenage pregnancies. The findings reveal that comprehensive sex education and one-on-one counseling were viewed as ineffective, while other interventions such as awareness programs and youth development initiatives received low responses. These results emphasize the need for alternative approaches and further research to develop more impactful strategies in these regions. The study also highlights the significance of parental guidance, responsible technology use, home visitations, and the positive impact of implemented programs in reducing teenage pregnancies and promoting overall well-being and education.

2. The research findings underscore the ineffectiveness of current interventions, such as comprehensive sex education and counseling, in mitigating the rising rates of teenage pregnancies in Alabat and Perez, Quezon. The lack of parental guidance and support,

irresponsible technology use, and the need for personalized home visitations and follow-ups emerge as crucial factors influencing the success of interventions. However, it is encouraging to note that some implemented programs in Alabat Island have shown promising results, indicating the potential effectiveness of comprehensive strategies in addressing teenage pregnancies and fostering overall well-being and education.

3. The study's findings provide valuable insights for the development of a localized Gender and Development (GAD) program to address teenage pregnancies in the study area. By incorporating components such as comprehensive sexuality education, community engagement, accessible reproductive health services, mentorship and peer support, and monitoring and evaluation, the program can effectively tackle the factors influencing teenage pregnancies. Engaging stakeholders and tailoring the program to the specific needs of the community will enhance its relevance and effectiveness. Implementing such a program has the potential to bring about positive outcomes and contribute to the overall well-being of adolescents in the study area.

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were offered:

1. To school heads, since the findings on teenage pregnancy was increasing and comprehensive sex education was mandated by the department of education, it is recommended to prioritize comprehensive sex education, foster a supportive school culture, engage parents, establish support systems, collaborate with external stakeholders, and monitor program effectiveness. These actions will create a safe and inclusive environment that promotes responsible decision-making and empowers students to make informed choices regarding their reproductive health.

2. To teachers, health coordinators, Reproductive health coordinators, Gender and Development coordinators, Nurses, and guidance counselor, since the finding revealed that the comprehensive sex education was the most applied strategy yet ineffective, it is recommended to properly monitor and evaluate the cases teenage pregnancy in your area, intensify the integration of comprehensive sex education into the curriculum, create a supportive classroom environment, promote open and non-judgmental discussions, provide accurate and age-appropriate information, and foster positive relationships with students. It is important to stay updated on best practices and resources for teaching

about reproductive health and addressing teenage pregnancies. Collaborating with school counselors, parents, and external organizations can also enhance the effectiveness of interventions and provide additional support to students.

3. To parents, since the finding found out that the most factor on the increasing of teenage pregnancy according to most of the stakeholders was the lack parental guidance and proper supervision, it is recommended open and honest communication with their children about sexual and reproductive health, including discussions about responsible behavior, healthy relationships, and the consequences of early pregnancies. It is important to provide accurate information and address any questions or concerns they may have. Encourage a supportive and non-judgmental environment at home where teenagers feel comfortable discussing these topics. Setting clear boundaries and guidelines around technology and social media use can also help prevent risky behaviors. Lastly, staying involved in their children's lives, attending school events, and fostering a strong parent-child relationship can have a positive impact on their overall well-being and reduce the likelihood of teenage pregnancies.

4. For health officers, Social Workers, Women and Children Protection Desk officers and Sangguniang Kabataan, since the finding found out an increasing number of teenage pregnancies in the municipal areas, it is recommended to actively engage in the development and implementation of comprehensive sexual and reproductive health programs within the community. Collaborate with schools, local organizations, and stakeholders to provide accurate information, resources, and services related to teenage pregnancies. Conduct regular training sessions for healthcare providers to enhance their knowledge and skills in addressing the specific needs of teenagers. Promote the establishment of youth-friendly clinics or services that ensure privacy, confidentiality, and accessibility for teenagers seeking reproductive health support. Additionally, participate in awareness campaigns and community outreach programs to educate parents, teenagers, and the broader community about the importance of sexual and reproductive health and the prevention of teenage pregnancies.

5. For future researchers, since the finding of the research was increasing number of teenage pregnancies in Alabat Island despite employed strategies, it is recommended to conduct further studies to delve deeper into the factors influencing teenage pregnancies, particularly in different cultural contexts or regions. Explore the effectiveness of alternative interventions that received limited support in this study, such as awareness of rights and protection,

youth development programs, and case management. Investigate the long-term impact of implemented programs on reducing teenage pregnancy rates and explore additional indicators of success, such as mental health outcomes and educational attainment. Consider incorporating qualitative research methods to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences and perspectives of teenagers, parents, and other stakeholders. Lastly, continue to collaborate with local communities and stakeholders to ensure the relevance and applicability of research findings, and promote the dissemination of knowledge and best practices to contribute to evidence-based interventions and policies.

References

- Albarracín D. et al. (2015) Theories of reasoned action and planned behavior as models of condom use: a meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*. 2015; 127(1): 142–161. doi: 10.1037/0033-2909.127.1.142. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- Allen, M. S., & Walter, E. E. (2018). Personality stability and change between age 12 and 14 predicts relationships, sexual activity and same-sex sexual attraction at age 14. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 74, 95–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2018.02.009>
- Araniego, J. (2019). Counselling services. Retrieved July 21, 2021, from <http://isis.fastmail.usf.edu/counsel/personal.html>
- Asnong, C., et al. (2018). Adolescents' perceptions and experiences of pregnancy in refugee and migrant communities on the Thailand Myanmar border: A qualitative study. *Reproductive Health*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-018-0522-7>
- As-Sanie S., Gantt A., & Rosenthal M., S., (2004). In the journal titled *Pregnancy prevention*. <https://www.aafp.org/afp/2004/1015/p1517.html>
- Bain L. E. et al (2020) Decision-making preferences and risk factors regarding early adolescent pregnancy in Ghana: stakeholders' and adolescents' perspectives from a vignette-based qualitative study, <https://reproductivehealthjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12978-020-00992-x>
- Babbie (2016). *The Basic of Social Science*. <https://www.researchgate.net/>
- Barnet, B., Liu, J., DeVoe, M., Alperovitz-Bichell, K., & Duggan, A. K. (2007). Home Visiting for Adolescent Mothers: Effects on Parenting, Maternal Life Course, and Primary Care Linkage. *Annals of Family Medicine*, 5(3), 224–232. <https://doi.org/10.1370/afm.629>
- Bogensneider, K., Small, S., and Riley, D. (2017). An Ecological Risk-Focused Approach For Addressing Youth-At-Risk Issues. *National Extension Youth At Risk*.
- Borrero S, Farkas A, Dehlendorf C, Rocca C., H., (2019) Racial and ethnic differences in men's knowledge and attitudes about contraception. *Contraception*. 2013;88:532–538.
- Broadus M., R., et al. (2015) An expanded model of the temporal stability of condom use intentions: gender-specific predictors among high-risk adolescents. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*. 2015; 42(1): 99–110. doi: 10.1007/s12160-011-9266-0. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- Carter MW et al. (2017) A qualitative study of contraceptive understanding among young adults. *Contraception*. 2017; 86:543–550
- Chey, C. O., & Khieu, V. (2017). Cognitive domain, level of difficulty and topic distribution of the science streaming the national exit examination in Cambodia. *Cambodia Education Review*, 1(1), 33–48.
- Children Net (2021). Problem Solving Steps for Parents. Retrieved on November 5, 2022. <https://raisingchildren.net.au/grown-ups/looking-after-yourself/communication-conflict/problem-solving-for-parents>
- Commission in Population and Development-POPCOM. (2022). Social Protection Program for Teenage Mothers Who are Minors and Their Children. Retrieved from: <https://popcom.gov.ph/dswd-popcom-team-up-to-address-teenage-pregnancy-in-the-country/>
- Committee of Publishing Ethics. (2018). Committee of Publishing Ethics (CoPE): Core practices.
- Copeland, R. J. (2017). Experiences of adolescent mothers in Costa Rica and the role of parental support. *Journal of Family Social Work*, 20(5), 416–432.
- Courtenay, W. H. (2016). Constructions of masculinity and their influence on men's well-being: A theory of gender and health. *Social Science & Medicine*, 50(10), 1385–1401.
- Clinton (2006). *Reconsidering Teenage Pregnancy and Parenthood*.
- Department of Budget and Management (DBM), NEDA and NCRFW. (2016). Joint Circular No.2016-1. Office of the President-NCRFW. Manila, Philippines. May 2016
- Derlan, C. L., Umaña-Taylor, A. J., Updegraff, K. A., & Jahromi, L. B. (2018). Mother grandmother and mother-father coparenting across time among Mexican-origin adolescent mothers and their families. *Journal of Marriage & Family*, 80(2), 349–366.
- Devkota, H. R., Clarke, A., Shrish, S., & Bhatta, D. N. (2018). Does women's caste make a significant contribution to adolescent pregnancy in Nepal? A study of Dalit and non-Dalit adolescents and young adults in Rupandehi district. *BMC Women's Health*, 18, 1–11.
- Education International (EI) and Education Development Center Inc. (EDC) (August 2016) *Building a Gender-Friendly School Environment: a Toolkit for Educators and Their Unions*
- Epstein, J. L. "Effective Schools or Effective Students: Dealing with Diversity", In *Policies for America's Public Schools*. R. Haskins and D. MacRae (Eds.), Ablex, 2016. (pp. 89-126).
- Epstein, M., et al. (2018). Adolescent age of sexual initiation and subsequent adult health outcomes. *American Journal of Public Health*, 108(6), 822–828.
- Fawcett, S. B., Andrews, A. P., et al. (2017). *Preventing Adolescent Pregnancy: An Action Planning Guide for Community-Based Initiatives*. Work Group on Health Promotion and Community Development. Retrieved from: [https://ctb.ku.edu/sites/files/PDF/Preventing Adolescent Pregnancy: - Community Tool Box](https://ctb.ku.edu/sites/files/PDF/Preventing%20Adolescent%20Pregnancy%20-%20Community%20Tool%20Box)

- Finley C. et. al. (2017). Stakeholder Education for Community-Wide Health Initiatives: A Focus on Teen Pregnancy Prevention. Retrieved on November 5, 2022.
- Fishbein M, Ajzen I. Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley; 1975. [Google Scholar]
- Frost (1995). Understanding the Impact of Effective Teenage Pregnancy Prevention.
- Gavin L, Moskosky S, Carter M, et al. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) Providing quality family planning services: recommendations of CDC and the U.S. office of population affairs. *MMWR Recomm Rep.* 2016;63:1–54.
- Gcelu N. (2019). The effectiveness of stakeholder collaboration in preventing learner pregnancy in secondary schools in the Eastern Cape, South Africa: Implications for leadership. Retrieved on November 5, 2022
- Glynn, J. R., Sunny, B. S., DeStavola, B., Dube, A., Chihana, M., Price, A. J., & Crampin, C. (2018). Early school failure predicts teenage pregnancy and marriage: A large population-based cohort study in northern Malawi. *PLoS ONE*, 13(5), 1–17.
- Gov Ph (2022). Proclamation No. 244 s.,1988. Women's Month Celebration.
- Grow by WebMD (2021). Teenage Pregnancy
- Grugni, A. (2018). Sex education. Bombay: St. Pauls, Bandra.
- Hang-Chuon, N. (2017). The paths of education reform. *Cambodia Education Review*, 1(1), 5–31
- Halonen A., (2017). A Comparison Between a Pregnancy Outcome in Women in 15-19. <https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- Harold, L. (2016, Nov. 22). CASSON canvasses counseling centres in tertiary institutions. *The Punch*, 39.
- Jemmott, L. S. (2016). Promoting Health Among Teens! (Abstinence Only). Program Success Center for Sexual & Reproductive Health.
- Kost K, Singh S, Vaughan B, Trussell J, Bankole A. Estimates of contraceptive failure from the 2018 National Survey of Family Growth. *Contraception.* 2018;77:10–21.
- Lee, K., Lawton, C., & Boateng, A. (2020). Parental experiences for teenage mothers living in poverty: Associations of head start. *Affilia*, 0886109920963032.
- Littell, J. & Wynn, J. (2017). The Availability and Use of Community Resources for Young Adolescents in an Inner-City and a Suburban Community. The Chapin Hall Center For Children, The University of Chicago.
- Nabugoomu (2020). Perceived Opportunities and Challenges of Family and Community. <https://www.ajol.info>.
- Manila Times (2020). How to Prevent Teenage Pregnancy.
- Merkh RD, Whittaker PG, Baker K, et al. (2017) Young unmarried men's understanding of female hormonal contraception. *Contraception.* 2017;79:228–235,].
- Mohr R., et al. (2019). The Influence of Educational Attainment on Teenage Pregnancy in Low-Income Countries: A Systematic Literature
- Morrison DM, Baker SA, Gillmore M. Using the Theory of Reasoned Action to predict condom use among high-risk heterosexual teens. In: Norman P, Abraham C, Conner
- M, editors. Understanding and changing health behaviour: From health beliefs to self-regulation. Amsterdam, Netherlands: Harwood Academic Publishers; 2000. pp. 27–49. [Google Scholar]
- Mosher W, Jones J. Use of contraception in the United States: 2016. *Vital Health Stat.* 2016;23:1–44.
- Odhiambo, J. N. (2018, December). Exploring the Underlying Causes and Psychological Consequences of Teen Pregnancy in the Philippines. In *International Forum Journal* (Vol. 21, No. 2, pp. 170-187).
- Odhiambo, J., N., (2018). Exploring the Underlying Causes and Psychological Consequences. [https://journals.aiias.edu.Official Gazette \(2015\) . Republic Act 1053 . https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph](https://journals.aiias.edu.Official Gazette (2015) . Republic Act 1053 . https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph)
- Okumu, A. L. (2017). Women secularism and democracy; women's role in the regeneration of society. A paper presented in The Conference on Sharia at Commonwealth Center, Commonwealth Institute, Kensington, London, April 14-15, 2017.
- Omeje, J. C. (2019). The role of counseling in improving instruction in tertiary institution: A case study of University of Nigeria, Nsukka. *The Journal of World Council for Curriculum and Instruction (Nigeria Chapter, WCCI)*, 4, 83-91.
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2018). National demographic health survey 2017.
- Philippine Commission on Women (2021). 18-Day Campaign to End VAW <https://pcw.gov.ph/18-day-campaign-to-end-vaw/>
- Philippine Statistics Authority (2020). Special Release Birth Statistics in Quezon: January
- Preliminary results. Special Release No. DVSS 2020-004 January 2020 Birth statistics.
- Philippine News Agency (2018). Teenage pregnancies in Philippines rise 70-percent over 10 years – UNFPA. Interaksyon.
- Phuhongsai S. (2018) titled based on the perceptions of community stakeholders on how can adolescent pregnancies be prevented, a qualitative study, Retrieved on November 5, 2022
- PopCom, (2019). CALABARZON Early Teenage Pregnancy.
- Rosenberg MJ, Waugh MS, Burnhill MS. Compliance, counseling and satisfaction with oral contraceptives: a prospective evaluation. *Fam Plan Perspective.* 2016; 30:89–92. 104.
- Raising Children Net (2021). Teenage pregnancy. <https://raisingchildren.net.au>
- Scharger, Olson, Behary et. al (2017). National Institutes Of Health. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>.
- Ramey, J.R. (n.d.). Working with the Media to Promote Teen Pregnancy Prevention. <https://aspe.hhs.gov/sites/default/files/private/pdf/174176/pch15.pdf>
- Shah et. al. (2016). Approaches on Teenage Pregnancy. <https://www.ajol.info>
- Shahabuddin et. al. (2017). Exploring Maternal Health Care Seeking Behavior of Married Adolescent Girls in Bangladesh: A Social Ecological Approach. <https://journals.plos.org>.

- Stanger-Hall KF, Hall DW (2017). Abstinence-Only Education and Teen Pregnancy Rates: Why We Need Comprehensive Sex Education in the U.S. PLoS ONE 6(10): e24658. Chicago.
- Strategies and Approaches for Prevention. (n.d.). HHS Office of Population Affairs. Youth.gov. (2021). Pregnancy Prevention.
- United Nations (2015). Sustainable Development Goals. <https://sdgs.un.org/goals> Youth Power Organization (2019). Community Empowerment. <https://tz.linkedin.com>
- UNFPA (2016). Annual Report. <https://www.unfpa.org> Xu-Kuan, C., Shi Wu, W., Fleming, N, Demissie, K., & Rhoads, G., (2017). Teenage Pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes: a large population based retrospective cohort study. <https://ncbi.nlm.gov>
- UNESCO (2018). Global UNESCO Meeting 2018. <https://en.unesco.org> Xavier et. al, (2018). Teenage Pregnancy and Mental Health Beyond the Postpartum Period: A Systematic Review. <https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>.
- Villanueva E. L. C (2017). Quezon province. <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Vaughan B, Trussell J, Kost K, Singh S, Jones R. (2018) Discontinuation and resumption of contraceptive use: results from the 2018 National Survey of Family
- World Health Organization. (2016). Adolescent pregnancy. <https://www.who.int/newsroom/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-pregnancy>
- Wynn, J., Richman, H., Rubinstein, R. A., Littell, J. (2019). Communities and Adolescents: An Exploration of Reciprocal Supports. Chapin Hall Center for Children, The University of

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jhohnniel P. Celeste

Ulpiano Camacho Elementary School
Department of Education - Philippines

Randy T. Nobleza

Marindoque State College - Philippines